

A Study on the Names of Town and villages in Mon Words in Bago Township

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Abstract

The Mons are descended from the Mon-Khmer tribe which belongs to the Mongoloid group, and settled down in lower Myanmar in 2000 B.C. They founded Sudhamavati city, Funanempire, Dvaravati city, Haripunca city, Hamsāvati city and Muttama city. Out of them, a line of 32 Mon kings ruled over the First Hamsāvati city from A.D. 573 to A.D. 794, the Second Hamsāvati city from A.D. 1369 to A.D. 1536 and the Third Hamsāvati city from A.D. 1740 to A.D. 1757 respectively. As those Mon kings were pious Buddhists, they built and repaired numerous temples, pagodas and stupas in Hamsāvati city. According to the years in which these religious buildings were built, it is known that the Mons inhabited that region by establishing towns and villages. Through the study, it is found that the names of some towns, villages and quarters in Bago district were derived from the Mon words

Introduction

The Mons are descendants of the Mon-Khmer tribe which belongs to the Mongoloid group. The Mon-Khmer tribe includes the Vietnamese, the Cambodians, the Mons, the Palaungs, the Was, the Mundas, the Sanbhas and the Khasis. The Mons migrated from Mongolia Plateau to the valley of the Yantzi River and went southwards. They settled down in the southern parts of Thailand and Myanmar in about 2000 B.C. They established Sudhamavati city in 1000 B.C, the Funan Empire in the 1st century A.D, Dvaravati city between the 6th century A.D, Haripunca city in A.D. 663, Hamsāvati city in A.D 573 and Muttama city in A.D. 1282 respectively. Out of them, the Mon kings founded the first Hamsāvati, the second Hamsāvati and the third Hamsāvati. Kings of Hamsāvati were devoted to Buddhism. Therefore, they built many pagodas, stupas and temples all-around Hamsāvati, which was their royal capital. The names of the famous pagodas and Buddha images among them are the Shwemadaw pagoda, the Kyaik-paw pagoda, the Kyaik-pon Buddha image and the Hamsāvati Buddhagāyā pagoda. The are names all these pagodas directly derived from the Mon words. King Dhammaceti, one of the Mon kings of the second Hamsāvati dynasty, endeavored for propagation and perpetuation of the Buddha's Sāsana by dispatching monks and laid people to Majjhimadesa and SriLaṅka. The Mons have been living in Hamsāvati region up to now. It is found through the study that the names of three quarters and eleven villages in Bago Township are directly derived from the Mon words.

Objectives

The Mons descend from the tribe of the Mon-khmer who belong to the Mongloid group. The home of the Mons was the Mongolian plateau north of the Gobi desert and thence they moved to the valley of the Yantzi River. When it came to 2000 B.C, they left the valley of the Yantzi River and established city-states in the southern parts of Thailand and Myanmar.¹

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¹ Nai Han Tha, မွန်အမျိုးသားလွတ်မြောက်မှုတော်လှန်ရေးဖြစ်စဉ်သမိုင်း (The History of Mon National Struggles), Yangon, Be-be Nay-zar Press, 2014, PP.1-2, (Hereafter cited as Han, Mon National)

The Mons founded Sudhamvatī city in about 1000 B.C. They established the Funan Empire in the 1st century A.D and it lasted up to the 6th century A.D. The Mons also founded Dvaravatī city (A.D 6th -11th centuries), Haripunca city in A.D. 663, Hamsāvati city A.D. 573 and Muttama city in A.D. 1282.¹

Out of those city-states, they established Hamsāvati city thrice in Lower Myanmar. Princes Samala and Vimala founded the first Hamsāvati city in A.D. 573² and a line of 17 kings ruled over it.³

The name of Seventeen ruling kings on the first Hamsāvati city are as follows:⁴

No	Name of King	Years of Accession	Years of Dethroning	Regnal Years
1	Samala	AD-573	AD-584	12
2	Vimala	AD-584	AD-601	17
3	Asakumma	AD-601	AD-608	7
4	Arinanda	AD-608	AD-615	7
5	Mahisaraja	AD-615	AD-632	17
6	Migidaraja	AD-632	AD-654	22
7	Migadippa	AD-654	AD-669	15
8	GijjadiyaRājā	AD-669	AD-679	10
9	Karavika	AD-679	AD-691	12
10	PaccalaRājā	AD-691	AD-704	13
11	Atthasara	AD-704	AD-719	15
12	Anurama	AD-719	AD-731	12
13	Miggadippa (youngest)	AD-731	AD-741	10
14	AggasamataRājā	AD-741	AD-753	12
15	UppalaRājā	AD-753	AD-765	12
16	PunnarikaRājā	AD-765	AD-780	15
17	Tisaraja	AD-780	AD-794	14

In A.D. 1369, King Banya Oo established the Second Hamsāvati city and a line of 11 kings ruled over it.⁵

¹ Han, Mon National, P.2

² Han, Mon National, P.2

³ NaiMaung Toe, မွန်လူမျိုးတို့၏ သမိုင်းအကျဉ်း (A Brief History of the Mons), Yangon, Kyon-ma-nge Press, 2015, p.62, (Hereafter cited as Toe, Mon Race)

⁴ (a) Han, Mon National, P.2

(b) ရွှေမောစောစေတီတော်ကြီးသမိုင်း (The History of Shwemawdaw Pagoda), Bago Mingalarthaung press, 2006, P.28 (Here after cited as Shwe, Pagoda)

(c) တိုင်းရင်းသားရက်စဉ်သမိုင်းမွန်, Ethnic History in the Chronological Order (Mon), Ministry of culture, Historical Research Department, Shwe-min-thar Press, Yangon, 2013, PP 3-6 (Here after cited as National Mon)

(d) Mamaka (Researcher), မွန်တို့ငှာနေရာမည (Ramañña, Native land of the Mons, 1st edition, Yangon, December, 1997, P.90, (Here after cited as Mar, Mon)

⁵ (a) Toe, Mon Race , P.109

(b) Shwe, Pagoda, P.28

The name of eleven ruling kings the second Hamsāvati city who established as follows:¹

No.	Name of King	Years of Accession	Years of Dethroning	Regnal Years
1	Banyar U	AD-1369	AD-1383	14
2	Raajadhirit	AD-1383	AD-1423	40
3	BanyarDhammaRājā	AD-1423	AD-1428	7
4	Banyar Ram	AD-1428	AD-1446	18
5	BanyarParu	AD-1446	AD-1449	3
6	BanyarKyan	AD-1449	AD-1452	3
7	Leik Put Taw	AD-1452	AD-1452	7 (months)
8	Shin Saw Pu	AD-1452	AD-1471	19
9	DhammaCeti(Alias) Rājādhpati	AD-1471	AD-1492	21
10	Banyar Ram Khait	AD-1492	AD-1526	34
11	Sushin taka Ryut Pi	AD-1526	AD-1536	12

In A.D. 1740, King Buddhakesi called Buddhakitthi founded the third Hamsāvati city and a short line of three kings reigned in it.²

The names of three ruling kings in the third Hamsāvati city are as follows:³

No.	Titles of kings	Years of accession	Years of dethronement	Regnal Years
1	Buddhakesi called Buddhakitthi	AD. 1740	AD. 1746	6
2	Nai Takki Khaing	AD. 1746	AD.1746	Months
3	Banya Dala	AD. 1746	AD. 1757	10

All Mon kings constructed and repaired many pagodas, monasteries, ordination halls, etc and dug lakes and ponds. The well-known pagodas built by them are the Shwemawdaw pagodas, the Kyaik-pon Buddha image, the Kyaik-paw pagoda and the Shwe-gu-gyi pagoda called the Hamsāvati Buddhagaya pagoda. Through the study of their history, it can be found that the Mons inhabited Hamsāvati region during the ancient times.

The original donors of the Shwe-maw-daw pagoda were King Mandalaik whose regnal titles was “samantaraja”, Mahāsāla and Cūlasāla merchant brothers, and people of Zaung-tu town. The construction of this pagoda was completed on Saturday, 1st waxing day of Tagu in the year 115 Maha Era. It is known that it was originally called ‘Kyaik-mu-ta’. ‘Kyaik’ means

¹ (a) Toe, Mon Race , P.109

(b) Shwe, Pagoda, P.40

² Han, Mon National, p.2

³ Toe, Mon Race, pp. 115-116

‘pagoda’, ‘mu’ ‘edge’ and ‘ ta’ ‘stand’, thus ‘The pagoda standing at the edge of the rock’. With the passage of time, ‘Kyaik-mu-tar’ was corrupted to ‘Kyaik-maw-taw’ through the intermediate term ‘Kyaik-mu-taw’.¹

The KyaikponPhaya includes four large Buddha images. King Dhammaceti built them in A.D 1475 to commemorate the Kakusandha Buddha, the Konagamana Buddha, the Kassapa Buddha and the Gotama Buddha, who had already been enlightened in this Bhadda world.² This term is pronounced (ကျပ်ဝန်) ‘Kyaik-pon’ in Mon in which (ကျပ်) ‘Kyaik’ means ‘pagoda or Buddha’ and (ဝန်) ‘pon’ means ‘four’. So it bears the sense ‘Four Buddhas’. Therefore, it is found that the Myanmar name ‘Kyaik-pon’ is directly taken from the Mon word ‘Kyaik-pon’.³

The Kyaikpaw pagoda was built by King Tissa, and his chief consort Subhudda (Talathaw) in the year 700 Myanmar Era. It was constructed to commemorate the removal of the wrong view (Micchaditthi) of King Tissa and his conversion to Buddhism.⁴ The term (ကျပ်ဝင်) ‘Kyaik-paw’ is corrupted from the Mon word ‘Kyaw-pon’. When Talathaw vowed in the presence of the king, the eight Buddha images came flying across the sky and descended onto the ground. Then, at the permission of the king, the pagoda was built right at the spot where the Buddha images had come down from the sky and named it (ကျပ်ဝင်) ‘Kyaw-paw’ in Mon, which means ‘The Buddha flying across the sky with his supernatural power’. Therefore, it is found that the term (ကျပ်ဝင်) ‘Kyaik-paw’ is directly derived from the Mon pronunciation ‘Kyaik-paw’.⁵

The Buddhagāyā Temple called ‘Shwegugyi Phaya” is located at Phaya-thon-zu village on the side of the Yangon- Mandalay highway three miles west of Bago. In the year 839 Myanmar Era (A.D 1477), King Dhammaceti sent 50 painters, masons and sculptors together with eight monks to Buddhagāyāin India. They noted there the measurements of the Mahabodhi Temple and the Sattasattahu Buddha images and the history of the pagodas and Buddha image. On their arrival back at Hamsāvati, on the 3rd Waxing day of Kason in the year 841 M.E, they started clearing away the bushes at Thale hill where the Mahabodhi temple was to be built. Then, on the 5th waxing day of the second Waso, the foundation stone was laid down for the construction of the temple.⁶

The term ‘Hamsāvati Buddhagāyāis derived from the Mon word (ဟံသာဝတီ) Hamsāvati Buddhagāyā’. It is assumed that King Dhammaceti built a Buddhagāyā temple in the same copy of the Buddhagāyāis temple in Majjhamadesa in his royal capital and called it ‘Hamsāvati Buddhagāyā’. The years when the pagoda and temples built by those Mon kings prove that the Mons settled down in those areas in ancient times by building towns and villages.

¹ (a) Moe MyintLwin, မြို့တည်နန်းတည်ဟံသာဝတီ ဘုရားစေတီ(၆)ဆူသမိုင်းအကျဉ်း (A Brief History of Six Hamsāvati Pagodas Built at the time of Construction of Hamsāvati) No names of Press and town and date of publication, obtained from No.0236 (Religious), library of Bago University. PP.8-10 (Here after cited as Moe - Town)
(b) ဥသာမဂ္ဂဇင်း(Ussa Magazine), Yangon, Thin Off-set, 1994, P.2 (Here after cited as Ussa, 1944)
² ဟံသာဝတီပဲခူးဘုရားမြို့ရွာ၊ ရုပ်ကွက်ဆိုင်ရာအမည်များလေ့လာချက် (A study of the Names of Pagodas, Towns Villages, Markets and Qurtors in HaÑsÈvatÊ Bago), Myanmar Department, Bago Degree College 2010, March
³ Mar, Mon, PP. 285-286
⁴ ဟံသာဝတီပဲခူးမြို့ဟောင်းဆိုင်ရာအထောက်အထားများ (Document on Old Hamsāvati), Bago College, 2006, April, PP. 33-34 (Here after cited as Vati, Old Hamsāvati)
⁵ Mar, Mon, PP. 283-284
⁶ Vati, Old Hamsāvati, P.7

It is found through research that the names of some towns, wards and villagers in Myanmar are Mon words and that the people continued to use them for successive periods. On the basis of these findings, the accounts of the towns and villages in Mon words in Bago township are to be mentioned emphatically and systematically in this paper. According to the census, there were 31 wards and 68 village-tracts in Bago Township in 2012.¹ Out of them, the wards such as Hamsāvati, Pan-Hlaing and Zaing-ga-naing villages such as Intakaw, Kaw-chay, Kamanat, Kin-paing-chun, Kyaik-dei-yum, Ka-twin-chin, Mukkala, Oh-bo, Saing-tee, Tarwa and Zaung-tu are taken directly from the Mon names.

The term ‘Bago’ is derived from the Mon word (ဘဝံ) ‘Bha-gwon’, which is pronounced (ဖဲဝံ) ‘Phe-gwon’ in Mon. Herein., (ဘ) ‘(phe) means ‘devising a stratagem’ and (ဝံ) ‘(go)’ ‘achieving’. Therefore, (ဘဝံ)Bago means ‘Town achieved by devising a stratagem’. The Myanmar word ‘Bago’ is taken directly from the Mon pronunciation ‘Pa-gay’.²

Zaing-ga-naing is derived from the Mon word, (ခိုင်ဂနာင်) ‘Zaing-ga-naung’, which is pronounced ‘Zaing-ga-naing’ in Mon accent. This word means ‘The village located near the Anan tree’. Thus the Myanmar word ‘Zaing-ga-naing’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘Zaing-ga-naing’.³

Kau-chay village is derived from the Mon word (ကံချဲ) ‘Kan-chay’ which is pronounced (ကော့ချဲ) ‘Kaw-chay’ in Mon. (ကံ) ‘(kaw) means ‘Island or land’ and (ချဲ) ‘(che)’ ‘Horse’. Therefore, (ကံချဲ)Kaw-chay means ‘Island or land of horses’. Thus, the Myanmar word ‘Kaw-chay’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘Kaw-chay’.⁴

Inn-ta-kaw village is written (အင်တဂေါင်) ‘Inn-ta-goung’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Ann-ta-gaw’ in Mon accent. (အင်) ‘(Ann)’ means ‘Lake’ and (တဂေါင်) ‘Ta-gaung’ means ‘Stream’. Therefore, (အင်တဂေါင်) Inn-ta-goung (Ann-ta-gaw) bears the sense ‘The lake fed by a stream’. The Myanmar term ‘Inn-ta-kaw’ is directly taken from ‘Ann-taw-gaw’, which is the pronunciation of the Mons.⁵

Zaung-tu village is described as (ခိုင်တာ) ‘Zaing-tar’ in Mon words and pronounced “Zaing-tar” in Mon accent. (ခိုင်) ‘Zaing’ means ‘Near’ and (တာ) ‘Tar’ means ‘toddy-palms’. Therefore, (ခိုင်တာ)Zaing-tar village means ‘The village located near a toddy-palm’. The Myanmar called ‘Zaung-tu’ in their accent in the past. But, with the passage of time, ‘Zaung-tar’ is commonly accepted as ‘Zaung-tu’.⁶

Kamar-nat village is described as (ကဝနာ်) ‘Kwar-naw’ in Mon and ‘Ka-mar-nit’ in Myanmar. (ကဝ)Kamar’ means ‘Lake’ and (နာ်) ‘Naw’ means ‘Divine serpent’. Therefore,

¹ ပဲခူးတိုင်းဒေသကြီးနှင့်ပြည်နယ်များအလိုက် ခရိုင်၊ မြို့နယ်၊ မြို့နယ်ခွဲ၊ မြို့၊ ရပ်ကွက်၊ ကျေးရွာအုပ်စုနှင့် ကျေးရွာများ (Bago Region, town, ward, village - tract and villages), 2012, August, Republic of Union of Myanmar, Ministry of Home Affairs PP. 90-91 (Here after cited as Bago Region, Villages)

² Mar, Mon, PP. 371

³ Nai Saraben, ဝေါဟာရဓာတ်မြစ် (Etymology), Lavi-hamsa Magazine, Yangon, Stationary, Press, 1981, P.68 (Hereafter cited as Lavi, 1981)

⁴ Mar, Mon, PP. 237-238

⁵ *Ibid*, P.427

⁶ *Ibid*, P.323

(ကဝနိ) Kwar-naw (ka-mar-nit) bears the sense ‘The lake of the divine serpent’. Thus the Manmar word “Ka-mar-net” is directly taken from the Mon word “Ka-mar-nit”¹

Tar-wa is described as (တဝါ) Tar-war in Mon words and pronounced ‘Tar-way’ in Mon accent. (တ) ‘Tar’ means ‘Toddy-palm’ and (ဝါ) ‘War’ means ‘field’. Therefore, (တဝါ) (Tar-way) bears the sense ‘The field of toddy-palms’. Thus the Myanmar word ‘Tar-wa’ is directly taken from the Mon word ‘Tar-war’.²

Mukkala is described as (မုနိကယ) ‘Mukha-ku’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Mukala’ in Mon accent. (မုနိ) ‘Muk’ means ‘Face’ and (ကယ) ‘(kala)’ means ‘Tiger’. Therefore, (မုနိကယ) (Mukkala) bears the sense, ‘The tiger face’. Thus the Myanmar term ‘Mukkala’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘Mukkala’.³

Kan-paing-gyon village is (ကင်ပါင်ကြိုင်) ‘Kan-par-n-gyan’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Kan-paing-gyon’ in Mon accent. The meaning of (ကင်) (kin) is ‘Guard’ and that of (ပါင်ကြိုင်) ‘Par-gyon’ is ‘The mouth of the creek’. Therefore, the Myanmar translation of (ကင်ပါင်ကြိုင်) ‘Kan-paing-gyun’ is ‘The mouth of the creek where there stands guard. Therefore, the Myanmar term ‘Kan-paing-gyun’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘Kan-par-n-gyan’.⁴

Hamsāvati is (ဟံသာဝတီ) ‘Hamsavatim’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Hamsāvati’ in Mon accent. (ဟံသာ) ‘Hamsa’ means ‘Brahminy duck’ and (ဝတီ) ‘vati’ means ‘The place haunted by sb’. Therefore, the Myanmar rendering of (ဟံသာဝတီ) ‘Hamsāvati’ is ‘The place haunted by Brahminyducks’. Thus, the Myanmar term ‘Hamsāvati’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘Hamsāvati’.⁵

Ka-twin-gyan is (ဒဒန်ကျာ) ‘Da-dan-kyar’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Da-dwan-Ryan’ in Mon accent, (ဒဒန်) ‘(Da-dwan)’ means ‘Bridge’ and (ကျာ) ‘(kyan)’ means, ‘crocodile’. Therefore, the meaning of (ဒဒန်ကျာ) ka-twin-gyan’ is ‘The bridge of the crocodile’. Thus the Myanmar term, ‘Ka-twin-gyan’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation, ‘Da-dwan-kyan’.⁶

Saing-tee is (စာင်ညောင်) ‘Sar-taung’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Kyaing-tee’ in Mon accent. The meaning of (စာင်) (kyaing) is ‘chicken’ and that of (ညောင်) (tee) is “abundant.” So (စာင်ညောင်) Saing-tee means “The place where young male chickens are abundant”. Thus the Myanmar word ‘Saing-tee’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation, ‘Kyaing-tee’.⁷

Oh-bo village is (အဝပ်ဗဟ်) ‘Aw-bo’ in Mon words and pronounced ‘Awat-bo’ in Mon accent. The meaning of (အဝပ်) ‘Awat’ is ‘Hide’ and that of (ဗဟ်) ‘Bo’ is ‘Look at’. Therefore, the meaning of (အဝပ်ဗဟ်) Oh-bo means ‘Hiding and looking at’. Thus the Myanmar term

¹ Professor Dr. Cho Cho Tint (Myanmar Sar), ပဲခူးတိုင်းဒေသကြီး: ဟံသာဝတီရုပ်ပုံလွှာ (Bago Region Hansavati Image), Yangon, Herbrew Press, 2011, P.184 (Here after cited as Cho, Hansa)

² Mar, Mon, PP.326

³ Mar, Mon, P.336

⁴ Interview with Mi Tin Tin Win, 69 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 1st Street, Bago. (6.6.2019)

⁵ Interview with U Chit Khein, 70 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 5 st Street, Bago. (6.6.2019)

⁶ Interview with NaiSoeThein, 75 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 1 st Street, Bago. (1.6.2019)

⁷ Interview with NaiBa Thein, 67 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 2st Street, Bago. (7.7.2019)

‘Oh-bo’ is ‘Hiding and looking at’. Thus the Myanmar term ‘Oh-bo’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation Awat-bo’.¹

Pan-hlaing is (ဝနံ့ခိုခို) ‘Pan-hlaing’ in Mon and pronounced ‘Pwan-laing’ in Mon accent. The meaning of is (ဝနံ့) ‘(pwan)’ is ‘Four and that of is (ခိုခို) ‘Laing’ is ‘The mouth of short creeks’. Therefore, the meaning of is (ဝနံ့ခိုခို) ‘Pan-hlaing’ is ‘The place where the months of four short creeks meet’. Thus the Myanmar term ‘Pan-hlaing’ is directly taken from the Mon pronunciation ‘ Pwan-laing’.²

Conclusion

The Mons are descended from the Mongoloid group and settled down in the southern part of Myanmar in about 2000 B.C. They founded Sudhammavati city, the Funanempire, Dvaravati city, Haripunca city, Hamsavati city and Muttama city. The establishment of these city-states prove that the Mons were an economically, militarily and politically high-civilized race. Out of these city-states, they founded the first Hamsavati (AD. 573-AD. 794), the second Hamsavati (A.D 1369-A.D 1536) and the third Hamsavati (A.D 1740- A.D 1757). The first Hamsavati dynasty had a line of seventeen kings, the second Hamsavati dynasty, a line of eleven kings and the third Hamsavati dynasty, a line of three kings, bringing the total number of the kings to 31. Therefore, it can be said precisely that the Mons lived in Hamsavati city with their own sovereignty since over one thousand years ago. The Mon kings were pious Buddhists and built numerous pagodas and temples all-round Hamsavati capital. In view of the Hamsavati Maha Buddhagaya temple built by the king Dhammaceti, which is in the same shape of the Maha Bodhi temple in Majjimesa, it can be known that there were religious and diplomatic relations between Hamsavati and India during his time. In the light of the years when those pagodas and temples were built by Mon kings, it can be assumed that the Mons have lived in that region since then by establishing towns and villages. The research has revealed that the names of three wards in downtown Bago and 11 villages in Bago Township are directly taken from the Mon words and pronunciation. This suggests that the Mon kings who reigned over Hamsavati used the Mon language as the official language. It is believed the revelation of the names of the regions of the Mon kingdom, their religious sites, pagodas, temples, pavilions and ordination-halls, their administrative centres, villages, etc, can yield some regional and historical documents to new generation of historical scholars. This paper is to reveal and present some religious buildings, villages and towns bearing Mon names through out the Hamsavati region.

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¹ Interview with Nai Tin Soe, 70 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 8st Street, Bago. (7.8.2019)

² Interview with Nai Win Thein, 55 years, Mon Sanpya Ward, 8st Street, Bago. (7.8.2019)

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ဟံသာဝတီပဲခူးဘုရားမြို့၊ ရွာ၊ ရပ်ကွက်ဆိုင်ရာအမည်များလေ့လာချက် (A study of the Names of Pagodas, Towns Villages, Markets and Qurtors in HansavadiBago), Myanmar Department, Bago Degree College 2010, March.

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